

OBTAINING Bst DNA POLYMERASE ENZYME FOR LOOP MEDIATED ISOTHERMAL AMPLIFICATION (LAMP) POLYMERASE CHAIN REACTION

¹Sh.Sh. Yusupov

¹N.F. Yusupova

Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

mail: yusufshakhzod@gmail.com

Tel: +998 99 465 41 30

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Importance of work: Loop-mediated isothermal amplification (LAMP) technology bypasses the time-consuming thermal cycle of conventional PCR due to rapid DNA amplification under isothermal conditions and is of importance. LAMP is also convenient due to its simple structure and minimal requirements for equipment. Its high sensitivity and specificity provide clear results, which are of great importance in medical diagnostics and the identification of pathogens. The versatility of LAMP is determined by its application in the detection of pathogens, genetic mutations, and various DNA sequences, infectious disease diagnostics, food safety, and environmental monitoring. LAMP contributes to advances in genetic research, microbiology, and virology. Its cost-effectiveness and role in early disease detection, including COVID-19, will have significant implications on public health initiatives. Bst DNA polymerase plays a crucial role in Loop-mediated Isothermal Amplification (LAMP) due to its unique features. It provides strong thermostability because it is produced in the thermophilic bacterium *Bacillus stearothermophilus* and allows maintaining activity at high temperatures. High accuracy provides results, which have a great place in diagnostics and research. The excellent performance of Bst polymerase under isothermal conditions simplifies the amplification process, reduces equipment complexity, and speeds up results. This is particularly useful in resource-constrained settings where advanced laboratory infrastructure is scarce, expanding diagnostic capabilities in underserved areas.

Purpose and Objectives of the Study: Obtaining Bst DNA polymerase enzyme for Loop-Mediated Isothermal Amplification (LAMP) polymerase chain reaction.

Materials and Methods: E.coli strain was used for protein expression. In this work, pET21A plasmid, lacI promoter in vector construction was used. Bst polymerase enzyme weight is 82kDA. A 6xHis tag was added to the Bst gene during enzyme isolation. This will help ease the extraction process. 5 µl of the Bst sample and 1 µl of ampicillin were added to the samples of transformed polymerases in 5 ml of LB medium at -80 C. It was grown for 1 day at a temperature of 37 C in a shaker at 250 rpm. Then 1 ml, 100 µl of ampicillin was taken from these cultures and transferred to 100 ml of LB medium. It was grown at 37 C for 3 hours. After the specified time, the OD indicator was measured. After reaching 0.7, the growing stage is completed. 50mM IPTG was added to Bst polymerase. Induction was carried out at 30 C for 4 hours. At the end of the induction time, it was centrifuged twice at 7000 xg for 20 minutes. The supernatant part was poured off, and the precipitate was sent to the separation stage.

First, the precipitate was lysed. Lysozyme solution, A and B buffers were used.

	A buffer	B buffer
Tris-HCL pH-8,	50 mM	50 mM
EDTA	1 mM	1 mM
Lysozyme	1mg/ml	

KCL		50 mM
0.5 % Tween-20		
0.5 % Triton 100x		

5 ml of buffer A was added and dissolved slowly, then incubated at room temperature for 30 minutes. After incubation, 5 ml of buffer B was added. Bst polymerase was incubated at 75 C for 1 hour. The Bst polymerase was centrifuged at 20,000 x g for 15 min. The supernatant was removed for the extraction step.

Results. The results show that transfection of a vector encoding recombinant Bst DNA polymerase into an Escherichia coli expression strain, followed by expression and purification by affinity chromatography was effective in obtaining highly pure enzyme in high yield. The purification process yielded a single recognizable band in SDS-PAGE analysis, indicating the homogeneity of the purified enzyme. [4] This high purity is essential to ensure the accuracy and specificity of the enzyme in LAMP reactions. Purity evaluation of purified Bst enzyme after buffer exchange revealed that buffer composition significantly affects enzyme stability and functionality. The buffer exchange process was successful in removing contaminants and replacing the buffer with a suitable composition, ensuring enzyme stability and functionality. This finding highlights the importance of optimizing the buffer composition for efficient use of Bst DNA polymerase in LAMP reactions. Comparing our results with previous studies, our methodology followed established protocols for obtaining and purifying Bst DNA polymerase. However, our study provides additional information on the importance of buffer composition in maintaining enzyme stability and functionality, which has practical implications for improving the efficiency of LAMP reactions. In summary, this study demonstrates an efficient method for obtaining and purifying Bst DNA polymerase enzyme for use in LAMP PCR. The high purity and stability of the purified enzyme, achieved through optimized buffer exchange, make it a valuable tool for research, diagnostics, and other applications requiring isothermal DNA amplification. Further research may focus on optimizing buffer compositions for specific applications or improving the yield and efficiency of the purification process.

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